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RETHINKING SUSTAINABILITY: TOWARDS AN OPEN SYSTEM APPROACH

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Abstract

Sustainability is a growing concern in architecture and urban planning due to the environmental impact of the built environment. Ecological challenges persist despite the proliferation of sustainable design strategies, prompting a critical reevaluation of existing approaches. This study examines sustainable design practices, focusing on the origins and processes of production, environmental impact, and socioeconomic dimensions. It also discusses 'cleantech' initiatives, which often prioritize profitability over ecological stewardship. The study advocates for a paradigm shift in urban design towards greater adaptability, complexity, and inclusivity, embracing porosity, incompleteness, and seed planning. This holistic approach emphasizes citizen participation and bottom-up interventions, reimagining urban spaces as evolving ecosystems. The study calls for a reimagining of sustainability that transcends conventional green design concepts, promoting a more resilient and inclusive built environment through an open system approach grounded in adaptability, diversity, and equity principles.

Keywords: Sustainability, Clean-tech, Open system design, Sustainable design

1 INTRODUCTION

In the 21st century, sustainability is the buzzword in almost every industry and field. Architecture and urbanism use this term often since the building industry is responsible for 40% of environmental damage. Various strategies, solutions, and technologies create sustainable design (Yazdandoust et al., 2023). Despite this, there is little change in the ecological problems, and they are even worse. The question is why everything stays the same despite many activities and efforts to create a resilient and sustainable environment. Do these strategies need to be reoriented to reach this goal, or are they wrong? To answer these questions, this study reviews some of the current sustainable works and the problems that make them unsustainable. These strategies emphasize the product while giving little attention to the origin of the process, which has an enormous environmental impact. Second, it explains how even the end product is primarily driven by profit, and it is just the greener version of its unsustainable version for the investors to make more money, as Goldstein calls "smart money." Climate change is unavoidable, so if we want to save the planet, we need to find a solution sooner rather than later. Therefore, in the last paragraph, this study refers to Richard Sennett's belief entitled "Open System," as discussed in his book called "Building and Dwelling." Sennett takes a different approach to finding a long-term, dynamic, and adaptable solution to climate change than his predecessors or contemporary experts (Sennett 2018, and 2006). There are plans for cities proposed by famous architects such as Le Corbusier to create environmentally friendly urban

contexts. However, despite being ahead of their time when suggested, they are closed and fixed, contrary to the concept of adaptation to climate change, which requires change as new aspects and challenges are revealed. Furthermore, Sennett's idea creates a more livable, healthier city by paying attention to the social life of humans, which also demands new skills from urbanists, architects, and city residents.

2 UNSUSTAINABLE ORIGINS

A new generation of sustainable technologies called clean tech reduces the negative environmental impact caused by current non-sustainable technologies. What are the differences between sustainable and non-sustainable technologies? Do they reduce the adverse effects of prevailing strategies? To what extent? Both technologies originate from an origin and go through processing and delivery before use. An essential aspect of sustainable design that needs more attention is the origin of raw materials and the excavation and extraction of these materials, which are crucial to preserving the planet. A well-known Australian architect, Murcutt, defined this importance by saying that sustainable architecture must "touch the earth lightly." Material selection is an integral part of his philosophy. The question is, "From where did the materials come?" Is there any damage to the land due to excavating that material? How will it be eventually returned to the Earth, or can it be reused, recycled, or put together in a way that allows it to be pulled apart, changed, and reused? (Guardian.com, 2016). Sustainable products, like non-sustainable products, usually involve excavation, mining, and processing that are not considered environmentally friendly. Kathryn Yousef, in her lecture "Geologies of Race," argues that material production is linked to injustice in labor work and power distribution regarding where mines are located and excavated versus where goods are used. She believes that effective architecture can only be achieved by considering the redistribution of power through preserving natural resources (Sennett lecture, 2019). That issue is also addressed in the book "The Red Deal."

Like the Navajo, Indigenous nations of the US are among the largest resource colonies, and they supply energy for many significant cities while lacking access to basic infrastructures like clean water and electricity, as explained in the book "The Red Deal." This applies not only to fossil fuel sources or, to be more precise, unsustainable sources of energy but also to renewable resources. Congo and Bolivia, for example, are abundant in cobalt and lithium. Lithium-ion batteries store energy from renewable sources using cobalt and lithium. Although the world's largest countries send heavy extract to these regions, they are among the poorest. Renewable energy has been more promising in creating more jobs, but it also has inequalities and injustices. As such, paying attention to overexploitation and heavy resource extraction is crucial. As the author says in *The Red Deal*, "Living well is not anthropocentric, or focused on human relations; it is Earth-centric, focusing on the whole picture." (*The Red Nation*, 2021).

3 CLEANTECH SUSTAINING CAPITAL

As well as paying attention to the product to be sustainable, clean tech must be economically sound before it can be environmentally friendly. There are innovative ideas for producing clean tech, but they need more financial support to survive if they are not profitable. Goldstein (Calvertjournal.com, 2022), the author of the book "Planetary Improvement: Clean-tech Entrepreneurship and the Contradictions of Green Capitalism," has studied the current sustainable movements by attending green venture meetings and workplaces and interviewing investors. He believes they are just putting their business under the banner of green. They have found a safer and more sustainable way to make money. As he puts it, "Green Entrepreneurship" looks for "Smart Money Making" through this networking. To exemplify the concept of smart money, he compares the clean-tech ventures with a television show called *Shark Tank*; each show includes a panel of "shark" investors evaluating fundraising pitches from a series of entrepreneurs who, if deemed worthy, will presumably invest their own money in the contestants' businesses. *Shark Tank* provides the opportunity to form specific investment relationships with specific investors who, like all investors, expect a healthy return. The show's drama revolves around the anticipation of determining whether an entrepreneur is "investable." Likewise, clean-tech investors create an intelligent relationship with a potential startup that can turn into a profitable market that is simultaneously benefiting from customers and investors. The market participants are attempting to pick winners and actively working to produce winners from the companies they have chosen to invest in. However, these investors introduce themselves as world makers, first and foremost, who will make an "impact" beyond capital and save the planet "we" live on. I put the impact of the words we use in quotes because what clean-tech ventures mean to them is unclear. Goldstein tries to clarify these terms: whose planet? Whose vision matters? Whose life is to be preserved? In his questioning, he explains that clean-tech technology, which pursues profit to create comfort for investors economically, culturally, politically, and emotionally, excludes the public. Thus, "we" refers to the specific bourgeois public composed of

entrepreneurs and innovators who invest in these technologies and whose vision matters to improving the planet's environment. Consequently, impact implies preserving this culture, and clean tech is considered impactful when it helps to keep the cleantech business by altering the customer's operations (Goldstein, 2018).

4 SUSTAINABLE OPEN SYSTEMS

Despite the challenges involved in turning towards sustainability, we still face environmental issues such as the disappearance of arctic ice, rising sea levels, desertification, extinction of species, pollution of air and water, water shortages, heat waves, and so on. Finding a solution is, therefore, imperative. Moving on from the small-scale issues explained above, this study will turn to large-scale and more fundamental problems with solutions that enable us to create sustainable societies for the planet's sake. Sennett argues that our city needs to be cleaner, safe, stimulating, efficient, and backed by a dynamic economy. He attributes this to the over-determination of modern cities determined to be in order and under control, both in visual forms and social functions. Thus, the contemporary city has lost vitality. Le Corbusier's "Plan Vision" for Paris in 1920 is a good example that replaces the historic center of Paris with uniform, X-shaped buildings (Fig.1).

Fig 1: Le Corbusier's Plan Vision for Paris, 1920 (Calvertjournal.com, 2022)

Fig 2: Garden city by Ebenezer Howard (Goldstein, 2018)

These towers eliminate the social life at the ground level, thereby removing the vitality and livelihood of urban realms. The plan vision became a model for other cities like New York and Chicago, resulting in the segregation of people with low incomes and people of color. Howard and Geddes created an ordered, balanced plan vision for a Garden city called a sustainable city by Lewis Mumford, who advocated planning, particularly in envisioning climate change (Fig 2).

This regulatory system can also be seen in recent smart city plans like Masdar City, U.A.E., and Songdo, South Korea, where a central regulatory system controls the whole city. Zoning and regulation are other aspects of pre-designed master plans that close the door to future vision. Implementing rules and regulations leads to conformity and draws attention to laws and regulations that could be more visionary.

Fig 3: Nolli's map of Rome (New Earth, 2014)

As a result, cities are frozen in the current time, while adapting to climate change and technological developments requires flexibility. He calls this type of city a closed system based on static equilibrium and integration. He believes in solving this problem; we need to look for open systems that are complex, dense, diverse, and able to evolve, emerge, and adapt. However, what is Open, and how can we design it? In *Building and Dwelling*, Richard Sennett defines the Open as a system that fits together with the odd. He further clarifies it with the definition by mathematician Melanie Mitchell: "A system is open in which large networks of components with no central control and simple rules of operation give rise to complex collective behavior, sophisticated information processing, and adaptation via learning or evolution." Therefore, the open system is non-linear, whereas a closed linear system can be broken into parts. Unlike a closed system that is clear and self-contained, and the power is accumulated at the top, the open system is complex, encourages differences and outside interactions, and distributes power equally through its entire social body. Before explaining how to design an open system, we must know who the designers of it are: an urbanist who is cooperative and self-critical, as well as people who live in the city. These people need to develop skills to manage complexity. Such systems require bottom-up interventions that encourage citizen involvement.

Sennett states that porosity is one characteristic of the open system; the open city is porous like a sponge that allows the flow between the inside and outside while retaining its shape. It removes the boundaries between built and open space, between public and private space. Noll's map depicts the porosity in Rome between solids and voids for the first time. In his drawings, the public spaces are white, while the private spaces are shown in black. This image, for instance, represents the round shape interior space of the Pantheon lit by a circular hole at its top (oculus) that was used as a church at that time in white, whereas the private house and some parts that are closed to the public are shown in black. (Fig. 3). To exemplify, Sennett compares the concept of porosity with nature. He explains that there are two types of edges: borders and boundaries. Borders are porous, whereas boundaries are not. The border is like a shoreline where the exchange of lake to solid happens, and it is where the organisms take their food sources or become food for other organisms. So, a kind of selective activity is involved in the border and is not random. Similarly, the borders in the city need to be porous, unlike the boundaries of modern cities, which are sheer dividers.

Incompleteness: another characteristic of an open system is to create incomplete forms. Unlike completely closed forms, incomplete structures are inviting and stimulating and can evolve through time as required. Indeed, incompleteness makes them more adaptable rather than fixed and finished. This can be done by leaving a form open or coexisting with other forms in the context. The urban fabric of old cities is an excellent example of how forms coexist, and if one form is eliminated, the others around it are affected. Pantheon in Rome coexisted with a less distinguished form in the urban fabric. Other examples are St. Paul's in London and Rockefeller Center in New York, which coexist with their surrounding context and stimulate them. An excellent example of an incomplete form is the housing project by Alejandra Aravena for poor people in Chile (Fig. 4). These incomplete forms make this construction affordable and allow them to expand once they can afford it.

Fig. 4: Housing project by Alejandra Aravena (Inhabitat.com, 2022)

Incomplete forms allow for adaptation when necessary. A competition was held after Hurricane Sandy in New York City in 2012 to find a solution for dealing with storm surges.

Fig.5: Dryline proposed by BIG Architects
(Architizer.com, 2022)

Fig.6: M.I.T.'s Living Breakwaters (*Scapestudio.com*, 2022)

Bennett compares two proposals: BIG Architects' Dryline (Fig.5) and M.I.T.'s Living Breakwaters (Fig.6). Dryline is a sand mound extending 10 miles across the tip of Manhattan, creating a social space with pleasure gardens, urban trails, and much detail. Living Breakwaters are underwater planted berms that erode and remake as storms pass through. Unlike BIG's visible and fixed (height and extent of berms) proposal, M.I.T.'s invisible proposal is adaptable and open to changes. Moreover, it is an effective solution for improving oyster habitats. It works with trauma and adapts to the problem rather than trying to mitigate it as Dryline does.

Seed planning: By eliminating underlying differences and creating homogenous visual forms, the last characteristic of an open system is to work on small-scale seed planning, which is adaptable, mixing, and complex. The whole is made up of parts that differ and have their properties.

Open systems welcome conflict, change, diversity, dissonance, and indeterminacy. Within this system, one can experience democracy in its true sense. A sense of 'us' is missing in a modern city, where people can interact and connect regardless of differences (Sennett, 2006 and 2018).

5 CONCLUSION

Implementing sustainable design techniques and solutions is imperative to overcoming the current century's energy crisis. The green movement began in the last few decades and is now one of the most popular activities. Sustainable technologies, however, are more focused on the final product, while the production process, including origin and delivery, remains unsustainable. Materials for these products usually come from rare natural resources, and they must be acted upon quickly to avoid being fully exploited and running out of resources. In addition to destroying the habitat of indigenous people and wildlife, mining and excavations also damage nearby ecosystems. Moreover, the labor for these excavations is provided by the already-dwelling inhabitants who are underpaid and overworked; plus, they need access to the necessities of life despite the abundant resources around them. In addition to the unsustainable process, the extent of sustainability of the end product depends on its profits. Innovative concepts are often abandoned despite their efficacy in reducing energy consumption if they are not a good investment. So, cleantech technologies have allowed existing technologies to have a green variant that will make even more profit. Despite the challenges posed by green movements, the disappearance of arctic ice, rising sea levels, desertification, heat waves, and other factors, we must find a way to mitigate the severity of these issues. Therefore, the research wrapped up by looking at some solutions, primarily those proposed by Richard Sennett. Sennett believes that the current design approach needs to be revised, making adaptation to changes brought about by climate change or other social and physical transformations difficult. Thus, replacing this closed and fixed system with an open system characterized by porosity, incomplete forms, and seed planning, for example, facilitates adaptation while creating a diverse, complex, vibrant, and dynamic urban environment that requires citizen participation to shape and maintain.

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